

VATARAKTA IN AYURVEDIC CLASSICS: A CRITICAL REVIEW

¹Dr. Garg Richa, M.D., ²Dr. Singh Keshav M.D. Scholar, ³Dr. Yadav Dipika M.D Scholar¹Reader, Department of Kaya Chikitsa, State Ayurvedic College Lucknow, U. P. India.²M.D. Scholar, P.G. Department of Kaya Chikitsa, State Ayurvedic College Lucknow, U. P. India.³M.D. Scholar, P.G. Department of Kaya Chikitsa, State Ayurvedic College Lucknow, U. P. India.

Article Received on: 26/11/2025

Article Revised on: 16/12/2025

Article Published on: 01/01/2026

***Corresponding Author**

Dr. Garg Richa

Reader, Department of Kaya
Chikitsa, State Ayurvedic College
Lucknow, U. P. India.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18107351>**How to cite this Article:** 1*Dr. Garg Richa, M.D., 2Dr. Singh Keshav M.D. Scholar, 3Dr. Yadav Dipika M.D Scholar (2026). Vatarakta In Ayurvedic Classics: A Critical Review. International Journal of Modern Pharmaceutical Research, 10(1), 54-65.**ABSTRACT**

Ayurveda the science of life is a comprehensive system of health care designed to increase our well-being and happiness in all aspects. Vatarakta has attracted the attention of world's scientists working on the problem, not only due to the problem faced by patient during acute attack but due to its remote complications and sequels. Description of Vatarakta is available since Pauranic Kala but detail description of its etiopathogenesis, poorvarupa, rupa, samprapti, upashaya-anupashaya and prognosis is available from Samhita Kala and Acharya Charak was first to give a complete picture of the disease Vatarakta. It described as a pathological condition arising from the simultaneous vitiation of Vata and Rakta by distinct etiological factors and generate the samprapti of Avarana. A comparative understanding of Vatarakta and Gouty Arthritis reveals significant overlaps in their etiopathogenesis and symptomatology. Both conditions involve derangements in systemic metabolism, peripheral inflammation, episodic flares, chronicity, and multisystem involvement. A systematic review of classical Ayurvedic literature reveals a wide spectrum of chikitsa modalities, including Samshodhana and Samshaman therapies. These therapeutic principles emphasize restoring Vata-Rakta balance, clearing srotas obstruction, enhancing Agni, and correcting metabolic derangements. This review synthesizes the classical conceptual understanding of Vatarakta. The insights derived may support the development of scientifically validated, Ayurveda-based therapeutic protocols for Vatarakta and related disorders.

KEYWORDS: Vataraktata, Samprapti, Virechana karma, Vasti karma.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda the science of life is a comprehensive system of health care designed to increase our well-being and happiness in all aspects. In the third millennium everyone is for seeking treatment of various ailments of body and mind beyond modern system of medical science. Majority of people globally have shown keen interest in AYURVEDA as awareness has increased because of adverse effects of powerful modern synthetic drugs.

In recent years, the miscellaneous groups of disease primarily involving the musculoskeletal structures have been the subjects of intense study. Various such diseases are responsible for much temporary or permanent disablement. Vatarakta is one of them. The Vatarakta has attracted the attention of world's scientists working on the problem, not only due to the problem faced by patient during acute attack but due to its remote complications and sequels. If the chronic condition is not treated

properly the deformity of joints and cartilages cripples a person throughout his life.

Vatarakta is a well-documented disease entity in Purana and almost all Ayurvedic classics, which shows that this disease was prevalent widely in early era too. Vatarakta is named based on dosha & dushya involved. It is derived from two words vata & rakta, which indicates the involvement of vitiated vata dosha & vitiated rakta dhatu in the development of this disease. According to Acharya Charak Vatarakta described as a pathological condition arising from the simultaneous vitiation of Vata dosha and Rakta dhatu where both Vata and Rakta are afflicted by distinct etiological factors and generate the samprapti of Avarana.

SYNONYMS

Various nomenclatures have also been depicted to Vatarakta by Acharya Charak namely Khuddha-Vata, Vata-Balas, Aaddhya-Vata and Vatarakta.

Table- 1: Showing synonym of Vatarakta.

Paryaya	Meaning
1. Vatarakta	The disease involving Vata dosha and Rakta dhatu.
2. Adhyavata	The disease which mainly affects the rich people.
3. Khudham	The disease which leads to Khanjata (Lameness).
4. Khudh vata	The disease commonly involving smaller joints.
5. Vatabalasa	The disease where vata is predominant.
6. Adhyarog	The disease affecting the rich people.

NIDANA

According to Ayurvedic literature, all the factors that are responsible to agitate the Vata, Pitta & Rakta causes Vataraktata. Various Nidans (Aetiological factors) of Vatarakta can be categorising into 5 groups.

1. Aaharaj Hetu - (Causes related to dietary intake)

- Atrasa sevana (Excessive use of food articles which are either salty, acidic, sweet, astringent or alkaline in nature.)
- Use of Tikshna, Hot, Unctuous and Dry food articles.
- Faulty dietic habits like-Adhyasan, Ajeernashan, Virudhashan, Alpa aahar & Anshana.
- Vidahi Aahar, Mithya Aahar, Rakta prakopak Aahar, Sukh bhojnam.
- Use of Tila paste, Radish, Horsegram, Blackgram, Bean, Green-vegetable, Sugarcane.
- Drinks like Vinegar, Butter Milk, Sura-wine, Medicated wine, Curd & Whey.

2. VIHARAJ HETU- (Causes related to activities and environment)

- Alteration in sleeping habits like day-sleep or awakening at night.

- Sedentary habits, Aquatic games, swimming, & Jumping, Excessive exercise.
- Suppression of natural urges like Urination, Defaecation, Abstinence etc.
- Forceful expulsion of natural urges.
- Riding on Elephant, Camel, & other fast-moving vehicles after meal.
- Improper use oleaginous substances.
- Improper conducts in particular seasons.

3. Mansic Hetu – (Causes related to mental status)

- Anger, Mental illness and usually bad psychological conditions

4. Aagantuj Hetu – (Exogenous factors)

- External injuries over the joints

5. Prakirna Hetu – (Miscellaneous factors)

- Person's delicate, obese and lazy in nature are highly prone to develop Vatarakta

Table No. 2: Showing nidana of "Vatarakta" as mentioned in samhitas.

Aetiological Factors	CS	SS	AS	AH	HS	MN	VS	BP	YR
[1] Aaharaj Hetu									
1. Rasa									
1. Ati lavan (excessive salt)	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
2. Ati amla (excessive acid)	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
3. Ati Katu (excessive pungent)	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	+
4. Ati Madhur (excessive sweet)	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
5. Ati Tikta (excessive bitter)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6. Ati Kashya (excessive astringent)	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7. Ati Kshar (excessive alkaline)	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
2. Guna									
1. Tikshna (sharp)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2. Ushna (hot articles)	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
3. Snigdha (unctuous articles)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
4. Ruksha (dry)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3. Faulty Dietic Habbits									
A. Quantity of Food									
a. Ati Matra (excessive diet)									
1. Adhyashan (eating on loaded stomach)	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
2. Ajeernashan (Predigestion meal)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
3. Virudhashan (Antagonistic diet)	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
b. Heena Matra (scanty diet)									
1. Alpashan (low diet)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2. Langhan (Fasting)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

B. Quality of Food									
1. Vidahi Aahar (Irritant food)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
2. Mithya Aahar (Faulty diet)	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
3. Rakta prakopak Aahar	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
4. Sukhbhojnam (favourable to satva)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5. Misthan Bhojnam (sweet articles)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C. Vidahi Annapan									
a. Vidahi Anna (irritable food)									
1. Klinna Mansa (decayed flesh)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
2. Shushka Mansa (Dry flesh)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
3. Jalachar Mansa (flesh of aquatic animals)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
4. Aanoop Mansa (Flesh of wet land animals)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
5. Palal (Flesh)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
6. Pindayak (Tila paste)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
7. Mulak (Raddish)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
8. Kulthi (Horse gram)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
9. Mash (Black gram)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
10. Nishpava (Bean)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
11. Shaka (Green leafy vegetable)	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
b. Vidahi Pan (Irritable drinks)									
1. Aarnal (Sour kanjee)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
2. Sauveera (Wine)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
3. Sukta (Vinegar)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
4. Takra (Whey)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
5. Sura (Wine)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
6. Aasava (Medicated wine)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
7. Madhyapan (Alcohol intake)	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
8. Dadhi (Curd)	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
9. Chukra	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
[2] Viharaj Hetu									
A. Swapn Viparyay (Alteration in sleeping habits)									
1. Diwaswpan (Day-sleeping)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2. Ratrijagran (Awakening at Night)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
B. Vayayam Matra (Exercise)									
1. Achankramanasheelanam (Sedentary habits)	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+
2. Ambukrida (Aquatic games)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3. Ambuplawan (Swimming)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4. Ativyayam (Excessive exercise)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C. Vega Vidharan									
a. Vega Nighra									
1. Mala, Mutra, Apan, & Prana Vayu vega dharan (Suppression of natural urges)	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
2. Aavyavaya (abstinence)	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
b. Vegouderan (forceful expulsion of natural urges)									
1. Ativyavaya (excessive coitus)	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
D. Riding									
Hastyashvastrayan (Riding on Elephant, Camel & fast-moving vehicles)	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
E. Sharir Shudhi									
1. Ashodhan	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1. Sneha Vibhram (improper use of oleaginous substances)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
F. Mithya Viahar (Faulty habits)									
1. Atikrodha (Anger)	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
G. Kalakrita hetu									
1. Ritusatmya Viparyaya (Improper Conducts in a particular seasons)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2. Hot climate	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[3] Mansic Hetu									
1. Atikrodha (Anger)	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+

2. Manha Santap (Mental depression)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3. Shoka (Grieve)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[4] Agantuj Hetu									
1. Abhighata (injuries)	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
[5] Prakirna Hetu (Miscellaneous factors)									
1. Sukumar (Delicate Persons)	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2. Stholya (Obese)	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
3. Stri (Women)	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-

SAMPRAPTI (PATHOGENESIS) OF VATARAKTA

The phenomenon beginning with vitiation of doshas, to the development of full-fledged manifestation of the disease with *dosha-dushya sammurchana* is known as 'Samprapti'. The treatment of the disease may be taken as Vighatan (breakdown) of Samprapti. So, the knowledge

of Samprapti is important before the treatment. However, most of the Acharya's have described the Samanya Samprapti or pathogenesis of Vataraktata. In Charak Samhita Vishista Samprapti is also described.

1. Samanya Samprapti (General Pathogenesis)
2. Vishitha Samprapti (Specific Pathogenesis)

SAMANYA SAMPRAPTI

VISHISTHA SAMPRAPTI (Specific Pathogenesis): in view of Shadkriy kala

SAMPRAPTI GHATAK

Dosha	-	Vata Pradhan
Dosha Anubandh	-	Pitta & Kapha
Dushya	-	Rakta
Updhatu	-	Sira, Snayu, Kandra
Srotas	-	Rasvaha, Raktavaha, Asthivaha Majjavaha
Adhithan	-	Sandhi
Srotodustilakshana	-	Sanga (Avarodha)
Agni Vyapar	-	Vishamagni/Mandagni
Rog-Marg	-	Madhyam Rog Marg
Swabhava	-	Chirkari (Chronic)

PURVA ROOPA OF VATARAKTA (Prodromal Symptom's)

As far as the Purva Roopa of Vatarakta is concerned certain preliminary local as well as general symptoms have been described in Ayurvedics texts. Since there is major involvement of vata dosha, rakta dhatu & twak in Vatarakta, many of the Purva-roopas are like that of Kushtha. Purvaroopas of "Vatarakta" as mentioned in samhitas are summarized in Table-3.

Table No. 3: Purvaroopas of "Vatarakta" as mentioned in samhitas.

S. No	Purva Roopa (Prodromatas)	CS	SS	AS	AH	MN	VS	BP	YR
1.	Atisweda Ya Swedabhav (excessive or loss of sweating)	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
2.	Karsharnya (Black discoloration)	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
3.	Sparsh agyatvma (Loss of sensation)	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
4.	Kshatetiruka (undue severity of pain on injury)	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
5.	Sandhi Shaithilya (incapability & weakness of the joints)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
6.	Aalasya (lethargy)	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
7.	Sadanam (Asthenia)	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
8.	Pidekoudgam (Appearance of skin eruptions)	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
9.	Janu, Jangha, Uru, Kati, Ansh, Hasta, Pada, & Angsandhishu								
a.	Nistoda (Pricking pain)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
b.	Sphuran (Throbbing pain)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
c.	Bheda (cutting pain)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
d.	Gaurav (Heaviness)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
e.	Kandu (Pruritis)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
f.	Supti (Numbness)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
10.	Sandhishurukbhutvabhutva Nashyati (Frequent appearance and disappearance of pain in joints.)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
11.	Twak Vivarnta (Discolouration of Skin)	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
12.	Mandalotpatti (Round eruptios)	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
13.	Daha (Burning in joints)	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	-
14.	Sopha (inflammation in joints)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
15.	Stambha (Rigidity)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
16.	Twak Parushya (Hardness of skin)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
17.	SiraSnayuDhamnispanandan (pulsation in vein, ligament & artery)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
18.	Sakthi Daurbalya (weakness in thighs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
19.	Bhavishyata Kustha sama (prodromatas similar to Kustha)	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
20.	Angasada (Body-ache)	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
21.	Twak Kantikshya (loss of skin lusture)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
22.	Ubhayapada Shathilya (weakness of both legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
23.	UbhayapadaSwedayukta (perspiration from both legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
24.	Ubhayapada Sheetal (coldness in both legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
25.	Ubhayapada Vaivarnya (Discolouration in both legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
26.	Ubhayapada Suptta (Numbnes in both legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
27.	Ubhayapada Gaurav (Heaviness of both legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
28.	Oshayukta ubhayapada (Burning in both legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-

ROOPA OF VATARAKTA (SYMPTOMATOLOGY OF VATARAKTA)

Symptomatology of Vatarakta described in two different ways.

1. According to the common site
2. According to their Doshic Anubandh.

1. According to the common sites of Vatarakta**Symptoms of Uttan Vatarakta**

- Kandu (Pruritis)
- Daha (Burning sensation)
- Rukayam (Pain on extension)
- Toda (Pricking pain)
- Sphuran (Throbbing Pain)
- Akunchan (Painful contraction)
- Shyavarakatamravarna (Blackish Red or coppery discoloration of Skin)

Symptoms of Gambhira Vatarakta

- Shavathu (Swelling)
- Stabdha (Stiffness & hardness)

- Antarbhrisartiman (Deep Agonizing pain)
- Shyavatamravarna (Blackish red or coppery discoloration)
- Daha (Burning sensation)
- Toda (Pricking pain)
- Sphuran (Throbbing Pain)
- Pakwan (Suppuration on the site of involvement)

Symptoms of Ubhayashrit Vatarakta

- Acute pain with burning sensation.
- Cutting pain in joints, bones & bone marrow.
- Causing deformity in joint & bones.
- Lameness, paraplegia
- Other symptoms including both Uttan & Gambhira Vatarakta

2. According to their Doshic Anubandh

A detail description of symptomatology according to their doshic anubandh are summarized in Table-4.

Table No.4

S. No.	According to Doshas Vata Pradhan Vatarakta	CS	SS	AS	AH	HS	MN	BP	VS	YR
1.	Sirayama (Distension of Veins)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Shoola (Pain)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
3.	Sphuran (Throbbing Pain)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.	Toda (Pricking pain)	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
5.	Shothsya Karshnya (Black colour swelling)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
6.	Raukchya (Dryness)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
7.	Shyavata (Blackish-Red colouration)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
8.	Shothasya Vridhi-Hani (Aggravation & suppression of swelling)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
9.	Anguli-Dhamni –Sandhi Sankoch (Contraction of fingers vessels & joints)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
10.	Anga-Graha (Spasticity of Limbs)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
11.	Ati-Ruka (Acute pain)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
12.	Akunchan (Painful contraction)	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
13.	Stambhan (Rigidity)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
14.	Sheetdwesh (Disliking for cold articles)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
15.	Sheet-Anupshya (Aggravation symptoms by cold article)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
16.	Veypathu (Tremor)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
17.	Supti (Numbness)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
18.	Shosh (Cachexia)	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
19.	Vivarnata (Discolouration)	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
20.	Mandiotpatti (Round eruption)	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
21.	Bhanjanum (Cracking of skin)	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
(B)	RaktaPradhanVatarakta									
1.	Sothoati Ruka (Swelling with acute pain)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
2.	Toda (Pricking pain)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
3.	Tamra Varna (Coppery colouration)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
4.	Chimchimayta (Tingling sensation)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
5.	Snigdha, Ruksha, Shamam Nayti (Non yielding to either unctuous or dry treatment)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
6.	Kandu (Pruritis)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
7.	Klinnta (Softening)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
8.	Dant Aur Rakta Shayava Varna (Blackness of blood & teeth)	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
C.	Pitta Pradhan Vatarakta									
1.	Vidaha (Burning Sensation)	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2.	Vedana (Pain)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
3.	Moorcha (fainting)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
4.	Sweda (perspiration)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+

5.	Trishnadhikya (Thirst)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
6.	Mada (Intoxication)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
7.	Bhrama (Giddiness)	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	Raga (Inflammation)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
9.	Paka (Suppuration)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
10.	Bheda (Cutting pain)	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
11.	Shosh (Atrophy)	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
12.	Sammoha (Mental confusion)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
13.	Sparshachamtva (Hyperaesthesia)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
14.	Shopha (inflammation)	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
15.	Ushamadhikya (Excessive heat)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
16.	Ubhaypada Teevra Daha Yukta (Severe burning in both legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
17.	Ubhaypada ushanta	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18.	Ubhaypada Rakta varna- yukta (Bilateral Redness of leg)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
19.	Ubhaypada shopha yukta (Bilateral swelling of leg)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20.	Ubhaypada Mriduta (Bilateral softness of legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
D.	Kapha Pradha Vatarakta									
1.	Stamittyā (feeling of wetness)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
2.	Gauravam (Heaviness)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
3.	Sneha (Unctuousness)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
4.	Supti (Numbness)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
5.	Mand Vedna (Mild pain)	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-
6.	Sheeta (Coldness)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
7.	Kandu (Pruritis)	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-
8.	Ubhaypada Kandu (Bilateral Pruritis of legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9.	Ubhaypada Sheetal (Bilateral coldness of legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10.	Ubhaypada Shopha (Bilateral inflammation of legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.	Ubhaypada peen (Bilateral thickness of legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.	Ubhaypada stabdhata (Bilateral stiffness of legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13.	Ubhaypada shyavta (Bilateral Blackness of legs)	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
E.	Dwandaja Vatarakta	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
F.	Sannipataja Vatarakta	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

SITES OF VATARAKTA

As far as the site of Vatarakta is concern most of the Acharya's have opinion that the manifestation of Vatarakta may starts from Hasta (Hand), Pada (legs), Angulya (Fingers) and Sarva-sandhiya (All joints) of the body. But it establishes primarily in hands and feet and then spread all over the body.

According to Acharya Sushruta, though it begins from the base of legs sometimes from the base of hands i.e. the most common sites are Metatarso or Metacarpophalangeal joints or Ankle & wrist joints. After then its spread's all over the body like Rat's poisons.

TYPES OF VATARAKTA

Two types of Classification of Vatarakta are available in Ayurvedic Samhitas.

A. According to their Doshic Anubandh.

B. According to the common sites of Vatarakta.

A. According to their Doshic Anubandh

All the Ayurvedic Acharya's has mentioned eight varieties of Vata-rakta

According to the predominance of Doshas.

1. Vata Pradhan Vatarakta
2. Pitta Pradhan Vatarakta
3. Kapha Pradhan Vatarakta
4. Rakta-Pradhan Vatarakta
5. Vata-Pitta Pradhan Vatarakta
6. Vata-Kapha Pradhan Vatarakta
7. Kapha-Pitta Pradhan Vatarakta
8. Sannipatik Vatarakta

B. According to the common sites of Vatarakta

1. Uttan Vatarakta related with Skin & Mansa of Sandhi- Sthan.

2. Gambhir Vatarakta: Occurs on deeper sites of sandhisthan.

3. Ubhayashrit Vatarakta Common features of Uttana & Gambhir Vatarakta. Amongst the Brihatraiae only Acharya Charaka has described Ubhayashrit Vatarakta.

Table No. 5

S. No.	Types of Vatarakta	CS	SS	AS	AH	CD	BR	MN	BP	VS	VR
A.	ACCORDING TO DOSHAS										
1.	Vata pradhan	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
2.	Pitta pradhan	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
3.	Kapha pradhan	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

4.	Rakta pradhan	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
5.	Dwandwaja	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
6.	Sannipataja	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B.	ACCORDING TO SITE OF ORIGIN											
1.	Uttan	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Gambhir	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
3.	Ubhyashrit	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-

UPADRAVA OF VATARAKTA (Complication of Vatarakta)

Total 24 complications have been described by Acharya Charak, Bhavprakasha, Yogratnakara and Vangasena, whereas Acharya Susrut has described only 12 complications. Acharya Vagbhata has not mentioned any upadrava of Vatarakta. Updrava of "vatarakta" as mentioned in samhitas are summarized in Table-6.

Table No. 6.

S.N.	UPDRAVA (complications)	CS	SS	BP	YR	VS
1.	Aswapan (insomnia)	+	-	+	+	+
2.	Arochak (anorexia)	+	+	+	+	+
3.	Shavasa (dyspnea)	+	+	+	+	+
4.	Mansakoth (gangrene)	+	-	+	+	+
5.	Shirograha (stiffness of head)	+	-	+	+	+
6.	Moorchha (fainting)	+	+	+	+	+
7.	Mada (intoxication)	+	-	+	+	+
8.	Ruka (pain)	+	-	+	+	+
9.	Trishna (thirst)	+	+	+	+	+
10.	Jwara (fever)	+	+	+	+	+
11.	Moha (mental confusion)	+	+	+	+	+
12.	Pravepak (tremors)	+	-	+	+	+
13.	Hikka (hiccup)	+	-	+	+	+
14.	Pangulya (lameness)	+	-	+	+	+
15.	Visarp (acute spreading infection)		+	+	+	+
16.	Paka (suppuration)	+	-	+	+	+
17.	Toda (pricking pain)	+	-	+	+	+
18.	Bharma (giddiness)	+	-	+	+	+
19.	Klama (exhaustion)	+	-	+	+	+
20.	Angulyavakrata (deformity of fingers)	+	-	+	+	+
21.	Esphot (eruptions)	+	-	+	+	+
22.	Daha (burning affection)	+	-	+	+	+
23.	Marma Graha (affection of vital part)	+	-	+	+	+
24.	Arbuda (tumefaction)	+	-	+	+	+
25.	Pranakshaya	-	+	-	-	-
26.	Mansakshya	-	+	-	-	-
27.	Kasa (cough)	-	+	-	-	-
28.	Stambha (stiffness)	-	+	-	-	-
29.	Avipak (indigestion)	-	+	-	-	-
30.	Visranva (spread)	-	+	-	-	-
31.	Sankoch (contraction)	-	+	-	-	-

SADHYASADHYATA OF VATARAKTA (Prognosis of Vatarakta)

Sadhya (curable) Vatarakta

- Navam (Recent origin)
- Ekdoshaj (Involvement of Single Dosha)
- Nirupdrava (Without complication)

Yapya (Palliable) Vatarakta

- Dwidoshaj (Involvement of 2-doshas)
- Akritasnopadravam (Few complications are present only)

Asadhya Vatarakta (incurable)

- Tridoshaj (Involvement of 2-doshas)
- Saupadrava (Associated with all complication)

- Shravi (with discharge)
- Vaivarnaya (Discolouration of Skin)
- Stabdhatta (Stiffness)
- Arbuda (Tumor)
- Sankochkar (contractures)
- Indriya Taapnam

PATHYA-APATHYA OF VATARAKTA

Regarding the Pathya-apathya (dietic and behavioral indication and contraindications) of Vatarakta given in various Ayurvedic literature are summarized in Table-7.

Table No. 7.

S. N	PATHYA AAHAR (FOOD)	CS	SS	YR	BP	BR	VS
1.	VEGETARIAN						
	a. Shuka Dhanya (Monocotyledons)						
	1. Purana Yava (old Barley)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	2. Godhuma (wheat)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	3. Nivar (wild rice)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	4. Shalidhan (shah rice)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	5. Shashtikadhan (shashtika rice)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	b. Shami Dhanya (Dicotyledons)						
	7. Aadhakya (Arhar, red gram)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	8. Shana (Chana, Bengal gram)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	9. Mugda (Mung, green gram)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	10. Kulthi (Kidney beans)	-	-	-	+	-	-
	11. Masoor (lentils)	+	-	-	+	-	+
	12. Makusthaka (motha)	+	-	+	-	+	+
	e. Vegetables						
	13. Suneshyank (Chowpatiya, marsilia Plant)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	14. Veytagra (sprouts of country willow)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	15. Kakmachi (black night shade)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	16. Satawari (climbing Asparagus)	+	-	-	+	-	+
	17. Vastuk (Bhathua, White goose foot)	+	-	+	+	-	+
	18. Upodica (Poei Indian spinach)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	19. Brahami (heliotrope)	-	-	-	+	+	+
	20. Karvellak (Karela, bitter gourd)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	21. Tandulaniya	-	-	+	-	+	-
	22. Prasarnai (Raj Bala)	-	-	-	-	+	-
	23. Shalichya	-	-	-	-	+	-
	24. Vridha Kushmand (white Gourd Melon)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	25. Suran	-	-	+	-	-	-
	26. Patol (Perval, pointed gourd)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	27. Amaltas (purging cassia)	-	-	-	-	+	-
	28. Dhatriphala (Amalki)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	29. Sheshapa (sissoo)	-	-	-	+	-	-
	30. Aguru (aloe wood, Eaglewood)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	31. Saral (long leaved pine. chirpine)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	32. Somavallae	-	-	-	-	+	-
	33. Mridika (grapes)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	34. Shweta Sharkara (white sugar)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	35. Erand taila (castor oil)	-	-	-	-	+	-
	36. Karpura (camphor)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	37. Kastoori (musk)	-	-	-	-	+	-
	38. Sheweta chandan (white sandalwood)	-	-	-	-	+	-
	Milk and its products						
	39. Aja Dugdha (goat milk)	-	-	-	+	+	-
	40. Mahish Dugdha (buffalo milk)	+	-	-	-	+	-
	41. Go Dugdha (cow milk)	+	-	-	-	+	-
	42. Maesha Dugdha (sheep milk)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	43. Ghrita (ghee)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	44. Navneet (butter)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	Non-Vegetarian						

	45. Vishkir Mansa (flesh of gallinaceous bird)	+	-	+	+	+	+
	46. Pratuda Mansa (flesh of pecker bird)	-	-	+	+	+	+
	47. Lava (lark)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	48. Titer (partridge)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	49. Murga (cock)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	50. More (peacock)	-	-	+	+	+	-
	51. Tota (suka = Parrot)	-	-	+	+	+	-
	52. Dadyha (wild parrot)	-	-	+	+	+	-
	53. Kapot (pigeon)	-	-	+	+	+	-
	54. Chatak (sparrow)	-	-	+	+	+	-
	55. Battakha (duck)	-	-	+	+	+	-
	Vihar						
	56. Mridu Samvahana (mild massage)	-	-	-	-	-	-
	57. Upnaha (poultis)	-	+	-	-	+	+
	58. Parishek (sprinkling)	-	+	+	+	+	+
	59. Pradeha (lepa)	-	+	+	+	+	+
	60. Abhyanga (massage)	-	+	+	+	+	+
	61. Sharanaya Pravatani Manogyani Mahanti (ventilated pleasant and large room)	-	-	-	-	-	-
	62. Mridu handoupdhanani (soft pillow)	-	-	-	-	-	-
	63. Shayanani Sukhani (peaceful sleep)	-	-	-	-	-	-
	64. Avgahana (tub bath)	-	+	+	+	+	+
	65. Sukhaushna Seka (mild fomentation)	-	+	-	-	-	+
	66. Na atiyarth Langhanum (mild fasting)	-	+	-	-	-	-
	67. Snehapana (intake of oleaginous substances)	-	+	+	+	+	+
	68. Raktamokshana (bloodletting)	-	+	+	+	+	+
	69. Virechana (purgation)	-	+	+	+	+	+
	70. Vasti (enema)	-	+	+	+	+	+
	71. Mridu Vaman (mild Emesis)	-	+	+	+	+	+
B.	Apathya	CS	SS	YR	BP	VS	VM
	Aahar (Food)						
I	Vegetarian						
	a. Shami Dhanya						
	1. Mash (black gram)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	2. Kulthi (horse gram)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	3. Nishpava (beans)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	4. Kalaya (pea)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	b. Vegetables						
	5. Muli (reddish)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	6. Ekshu (sugar cane)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	7. Pidyak (tila paste)	-	-	-	-	-	-
	8. Tambul (betel)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	9. Tila (sesamum)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	c. Drinks						
	10. Kanji (sour kanji)	-	-	-	-	-	-
	11. Madhya (liquor)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	12. Dadhi (curd)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	13. Sattu (flour of roasted food grains)	-	-	+	-	-	-
II	Non-Vegetarian						
	14. Ambuj Prani Mansa (flesh of aquatic animal)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	15. Aanoop prani Mansa (flesh of wet land animal)	-	-	+	-	-	-
III	Rasa						
	16. Amla (acid)	+	+	-	+	+	+
	17. Lavan (salt)	+	+	+	+	+	+
	18. Katu (pungent)	+	-	+	+	+	+
IV	Guna						
	19. Guru (heavy)	+	+	+	+	+	+
	20. Ushna (hot)	+	+	+	+	+	+

	21. Abhishyandi	+	+	+	+	+	+
	22. Virudha Aahar (antagonistic diet)	-	-	+	-	-	-
	Vihar						
	23. Divaswapan (day sleep)	+	+	+	+	+	+
	24. Vayayam (exercise)	+	-	+	+	-	+
	25. Aatap (heat of sun)	+	+	+	+	+	+
	26. Maithun (coitus)	-	-	+	-	+	-
	27. Sharam (labour)	-	-	-	-	+	-
	28. Kopa (anger)	-	+	-	+	-	-

CHIKITSA OF VATARAKTATA

SAMANYA CHIKITSA OF VATARAKTA - Further classified into two groups:

(a) Bahir Shodhan (b) Antaha Shodhan

(a) **Bahir Shodhan** - In case of Vatarakta blood should be let out with Horn, Leech, Needle, Bottle-gourd & Venesection according to Dosha and Bala of the patients.

(b) **Antaha Shodhan** - Patient of Vatarakta should first be oiled and then purgated using Sneha yukta Virechan Dravyas (unctuous purgatives) or by Ruksha (dry) mild purgative dravyas. Frequent Vasties (Medicated Enema) should be administered, Pradeha (lepa) Saika (Fomentation), Abhayanga (Massage) with diet control.

2. VISHISTHA CHIKITSA OF VATARAKTA

(A) Chikitsa according to site

Treatment of Uttan Vatarakta

- Alepan (Application of Medicated lepa)
- Abhyanga (Medicated Massage)
- Parisheka (sprinkling of Medicated Kwath or Swarasa etc.)
- Upanaha (Medicated Poultis)

Treatment of Gambhira Vatarakta

- Snehana (oleation)
- Virechana (Purgation)

- Vasti (Medicated Enema)

(B) Chikitsa according to Doshic Predominance

1. In Vata Pradhan Vatarakta

Use of Sneha like Ghrith, Taila, Vasa (fat) and Majja in the form of Pana, Abhyangan (Massage) & Anuvasan Vasti and Hot poultice.

2. In Rakta-Pitta Pradhan Vatarakta

Use of Purgative for Virechana, Ghrith & Milk for Pana and Foementation & Vasti Karma along with cool & refrigerent application of Medicines.

3. In Kapha Pradhan Vatarakta

Use of Mild emetic's, Mild Oleation, Foementation, Fasting and Warm lepa.

SANSHAMAN CHIKITSA

Various herbomineral compounds advocated in Ayurveda for the treatment of *Doshik* and *Sthanik* varieties of Vatarakta are as follows.

Table no.- 7.

1.	Lepa	Tiladi lepa, Daha Nashak lepa, Madhuchist lepa, Tagaradi lepa
2.	Churna	Nimbadi churna, Munditika churna, Guduchi churna
3.	Swarasa	Guduchi Swarasa
4.	Avleha	Amritadhyavleha
5.	Kalka	Amritadi kalka, Triphaladi kalka, Katukadi kalka, Shigru beej kalka, Guduchi kalka
6.	Yoga	Yogasaramita, Guduchi yoga, Guduchyastya yoga, Godhuma churnadi yoga, Gurhbhrit yoga
7.	Kwatha	Amritadi kwatha, Triphala kwath, Kashmaryadi kwatha, Guduchyadi kwatha, Ashwath kwatha, Lagu manjisthadi kwatha, Shalparni kwatha
8.	Ghritha	Mahatikta ghritha, Parushak ghritha, Dwepanchmuladi ghritha, Drakchadi ghritha, Padamkadi ghritha, Guduchi ghritha, Mahaguduchi ghritha, Amritadhya ghritha (Pratham, Dwitiya)
9.	Taila	Sukumar taila, Amritadi taila, Mahapadamkadi taila, Dashpak Bala taila, Shatpak Bala taila, Pinda taila, Perpinda taila, Mahapinda taila, Guduchi taila, Maharudra taila, VishaTinduk taila, Rudra taila, Maharudra taila,
10.	Ksheer	Drakshadi ksheer, Baladi ksheer, Dashmuladi ksheer
11.	Gutika	Langli gutika, Chandra prabha gutika, Guggulu vati, Surya prabha vati
12.	Guggulu	Punarnava guggulu, Amrita guggulu, Kaishor guggulu, Triphala guggulu, S inghnada guggulu, Rasabhra guggulu
13.	Rasaushadhi	Vataraktantak rasa, Vishvayshwer rasa, Dwadshayas Mahataleshwar rasa, Servayshwar rasa, Panchamrit rasa

14.	Lauha	Langlyadhya lauha, Guduchiyadhya lauha, Pittantak lauha
15.	Bhasma	Tal-bhasma

REFERENCES

1. Kumar R., Pt. Sharma, R. S. Sanatani Dharma, Ptaka, Moradadad Sambad Atharvaveda Hindi Commentary by, 1986.
2. Garun Puran: Maharishi Vedvyas - Ed - By Bhattacharya R.S.- Edition - 1964 Chaukhamba Sanskrit Series Varanasi.
3. Agni Puran: By Maharishi Vedvyas, Gurumandal Series number XVII, 5 clive Row 1957.
4. Pandey K, Chaturvedi G. Charaka Samhita Savimarsha Vidyotini 9th ed. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan; 2009. Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter 29, Verse 11 p.748.
5. Chakrapani Agnivesha Charak samhita, Vaidya Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, Varanasi, Chaukhamba sanskrita sansthana 5th edition 2001.
6. Chakrapani dutta, Chakradatta, Vaidyaprabha hindi vyakhya Sri Indra deva Tripathi, Varanasi, Chaukhamba Sanskrit series, edition 2005.
7. Shastri A Sushruta Samhita, Ayurvedatattva Sandipika 2nd ed. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan; 2010. Nidana Sthana, Chapter 1Verse 48 p.300.
8. Tripathi B. Ashtanga Hridaya, Nirmala vyakhaya, Reprint Edition Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan; 2009. Nidana Sthana, Chapter 16, Verse 5-6 p.280.
9. Madhav Nidan with Madhukosh commentary with extracts from Atankadarpana by Vd. Vachaspati Vaidya; Chaukhamba Orientalia, edition 2006.
10. Yoga Ratnakar with vidyotini commentary by Vd.Shree Lakshmipati Shastri; Chaukhamba Sanskrit sansthan Varanasi, 7th edition 1999.
11. Mishra S.N Bhaisajya Ratnavali. Siddhiprada Hindi Commentary; Reprint Edition Varanasi: Chaukhamba Prakashan; 2009 Vatarakta Rogadhikar, chapter 27, Verse 133-134. p. 585.
12. Gad Nigraha of Shri Vaidya Sodhal with Hindi Vidyotini commentary by Shri Indredeva Tripathi edited by shri Ganga Sahay Pandey part -2.
13. Shri Venkateshwar Vangsenia Samhita. Hindi translation. Steam Press Bombay; Chapter: vatarakta Nidana, verse 45-46.
14. Singh A. Amarkosh Ayurveda Shabdakosh.
15. Vachaspatyam by Brihatta sanskrit abhidhanam Shri Taranath Bhattacharya.Voll.VI.
16. Shastri r.; Vedo Mein Ayurveda Madan Mohanlal Ayurvedic Anusandhan Trust; 1st edition.